

THE RUSSIA-UKRAINE WAR AND GAZA CRISIS: REFUGEES AND THE ROLE OF KEY ACTORS

Aman Bora

Abstract

This comparative study analyses displacement trends and humanitarian responses in the Russia-Ukraine conflict and the Gaza catastrophe. It compares the size, demographic effect, access to fundamental services, and the involvement of states, international organisations, and NGOs using reliable operational data and public monitoring reports. The article finds that both crises create urgent humanitarian needs, but that disparities in access, international coordination, and legal protections create unique protection gaps. It suggests that targeted, context-specific actions be taken to improve protection, share the burden, and develop long-term solutions.

KEYWORDS: Russia-Ukraine war, Gaza, Refugee, Humanitarian Crisis, Displacement.

INTRODUCTION

Every year, millions of people are displaced due to wars, conflicts, and political instability. The recent Russia-Ukraine War and the Gaza conflict have caused major humanitarian crises and have global protection mechanisms, and have resulted in the most substantial forced displacement of the 21st century. The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) report mentions that at the end of 2024, there were 42.7 million refugees around the world, the most ever recorded (UNHCR 2025a, 7, 35). The Russia-Ukraine war and the Gaza conflict are two examples of the current refugee crisis. Both have displaced millions from their homes due to conflict, persecution, and insecurity, exerting significant strain on host communities and the international protection framework. This paper examines the root causes, dimensions, and humanitarian consequences of these crises, and evaluates the responses of states, intergovernmental organisations, and NGOs. At this juncture, it becomes necessary to outline the international legal definition of a refugee, which frames the subsequent analysis. Refugee (1951 Convention, Art. 1): *'a person who, owing to a well-founded fear of persecution for reasons such as race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group or political opinion, is outside the country of nationality and is unable or unwilling to avail themselves of that country's protection'* (UNHCR 2011). With this framework in place, it is now possible to examine the underlying political, social, and security factors that have led to the current refugee crises.

DRIVERS OF THE REFUGEE CRISIS

Russia-Ukraine War

Russian actions since 2014, such as taking over Crimea and backing separatists, finally led to the full-scale invasion in 2022, which caused the most significant displacement in Europe since WWII. Analysts argue that Russia's concerns about NATO's expansion and its desire for more territory triggered the conflict (Masters 2023; Okemini 2023). The war has hurt many civilians and forced many people to leave their homes. In September 2025, following Russia's invasion, the UNHCR had counted more than 5.7 million Ukrainian refugees around the world (UNHCR 2025b). Some analysts claim that President Vladimir Putin seeks to regain Russia's control over former Soviet territory, which they refer to as '*Putin's Imperial Ambitions*' (Torbakov 2022; Khrushcheva 2022). From another perspective, the invasion might be seen as a pre-emptive measure to deter Ukraine from aligning with Western alliances, which Russia views as a potential threat to national security. Russia has, at different times and platforms, expressed serious worry over the expansion of NATO and the EU into Eastern Europe. Götz and Ekman (2024, 199) assert that one of the primary catalysts for Russia's attack was Ukraine's growing political and strategic alignment with Western countries.

Gaza Crisis

The Gaza conflict, rooted in intermittent violence between Israeli and Palestinian groups, has been ongoing for decades. The 1948 Arab-Israeli War, which Palestinians name the Nakba (*'the Catastrophe'*), is where the issue began. This conflict led to the foundation of Israel and the loss of homes and land for more than 7,50,000 Palestinians between 1947 and 1959 (Irfan 2023, 25), which started a major refugee problem. As of 2023, around 75 per cent of Gaza's 2.3 million residents are registered refugees (Farhat et al. 2023, 2). On October 7, 2023, armed Palestinian organisations, Hamas, fired missiles at Israel, breaking through the border fence and killing 1200 Israelis and taking 240 people hostage. Following a '*state of war alert*,' the Israeli military launched attacks, causing thousands of deaths and displacements. Israel's defence minister said there would be a '*total siege*,' which would cut off food, water, fuel, and electricity to everyone (Abudayya 2025, 2). This was seen as a sort of collective punishment and a possible war crime. Since then, violence has caused mass displacement, key services to fail, and an artificial famine.

THE HUMANITARIAN CRISIS

The wars in Ukraine and Gaza have caused humanitarian disasters, causing much pain for civilians through deaths, displacement, and the shutdown of essential services. Even though the situations are different, both wars have caused deep and lasting disasters for people. It is hard to verify exact casualty numbers because both sides share distinct narratives. However, official verified records of the UN Human Rights Monitoring Mission in Ukraine claim that at least 14,054 civilians have died, including 730 children, and 36,164 civilians have been hurt, including 2,263 children (Jenča 2025). Ukrainian President Zelensky claimed in December 2024 that 43,000 Ukrainian fighters had died and 3,70,000 had been wounded (Binley and Beale 2024). As of June 12, 2025, another source says that a total of 1,70,521 Ukrainians and Russians have died, including soldiers and civilians (Court 2025).

Russian attacks have damaged civilian infrastructure in Ukraine. More than half of Ukraine's electricity supply has been damaged, which has affected the supply of gas, water, and energy. By August 2022, there had already been 445 attacks on healthcare facilities (Poberezhets 2022, 315–16). An estimated 55,000 houses were damaged or destroyed in the first year of the full-scale invasion (Okemini 2023, 250). In February 2025, the World Bank, the UN, the European Commission, and the Ukrainian Government released a joint report that said it would cost \$524 billion to reconstruct Ukraine's economy (World Bank 2025).

About 1.9 million Palestinians, or more than 90 per cent of Gaza's population, are displaced (UN 2025b). By July 31, 2025, 9,735 women and 18,430 children died in Gaza (OCHA 2025b). The Ministry of Health estimated that at least 65,062 Palestinians had died and 165,697 had been wounded by August 27, 2025 (OCHA 2025c). The UN Secretary-General has said that Gaza is now a *'graveyard for children.'* The UN Women's office said that since the fighting started, two mothers in Gaza had died every hour. About 19,000 kids have lost their parents since October 2023. In addition to this, other sectors have been hit hard too:

- The war has damaged the food supply chain, and as of January 2024, 34.2 per cent of farmland has been degraded (Buheji and Hasan 2024, 12). This destruction, together with the embargo, has caused extreme food insecurity and a proven famine in some parts of Gaza.
- There is a substantial rise in child malnutrition in Gaza. The number of extremely malnourished children went from 8.3 per cent in July to 13.5 per cent in August 2025. In Gaza City, it was 19 per cent. About 12,800 kids were very malnourished, and the number of instances of Severe Acute Malnutrition climbed to 23 per cent (UNICEF 2025).

- More than 91 per cent of households now face a very high risk of not having enough water, and around 88 per cent of schools have been damaged, effectively rendering the education system almost non-existent (Abudayya 2025, 2).

INTERNATIONAL RESPONSE

External actors, including UN agencies, international bodies, and NGOs, have played a crucial but challenging role in addressing the humanitarian crises in both Ukraine and Gaza.

International Organisations and NGOs

Conflict frequently results in the relocation of a significant population, rendering them susceptible. A similar situation is visible in both Ukraine and Gaza, but in an unfair comparison, the situation of Gazans is much worse than in Ukraine. NGOs play a vital role in the worldwide response to crises by providing humanitarian aid, proactive measures, conflict mediation, development support and establishing institutions. They are often the first to respond to complex emergencies due to the nature of their primary aim. In addition, as Schwartz (2016, 49) has noted, they serve as advocates for those affected and as critics of governmental and international policies.

In Ukraine

In a brief period, Ukrainians saw a sudden and complete disruption to their life, with their state under attack and a significant number of citizens unexpectedly displaced from their homes. Organisations globally swiftly responded to what Thompson and Wolfe (2022) proclaimed as one of the most substantial humanitarian disasters in contemporary history. According to the UN OCHA, more than 600 groups, 70 per cent of which are local NGOs, are assisting with the humanitarian response in Ukraine (OCHA 2025c). As of the middle of 2025, humanitarian partners have assisted 3.6 million of the 12.7 million people who required some form of support. Amidst the Ukraine crisis, these organisations performed crucial roles in addressing the humanitarian needs. UNHCR has been in charge of coordinating the regional response. It has helped refugees and internally displaced people (IDPs) by giving them protection services, emergency shelter, and basic needs. The Red Cross, UNICEF, WHO, Doctors Without Borders and other major organisations are on the ground. Apart from humanitarian assistance, some organisations are also monitoring the risk of corruption. For example, Nashi Groshi, an anti-corruption NGO, uncovered a fraud worth \$355 million, leading to several resignations and reforms (Deprez 2023).

Through its different agencies, the UN is at the forefront of providing aid and assistance to both Ukraine and Gaza. The UN OCHA and its partners have played a crucial role in delivering assistance to the Ukrainian population. The Humanitarian Needs and Response Plan helped 8.4 million people in Ukraine in 2024 (OCHA 2025a). The UN has consistently urged all parties involved in the conflict to safeguard the rights of civilians and comply with international humanitarian law and has been aiding the Ukrainian government in its efforts to mitigate the economic and social repercussions of the conflict. This involves the implementation of community resilience and recovery initiatives that focus on rebuilding affected areas and supporting the return of displaced residents.

In Gaza

Since Israeli Defence Minister Yoav Gallant declared a total blockade on the Gaza Strip on October 9, 2023, Palestinians have persistently faced ongoing confinement in increasingly cramped and densely populated regions that are severely lacking in the necessary resources to sustain human existence. The continuous aerial bombardment has resulted in almost the entire civilian population of Gaza depending on humanitarian help for their survival. The Red Cross President, SP Egger, described the suffering in Gaza as *'intolerable'* and *'beyond anything that anyone should be in a position to describe'* (AFP 2023). Several UN organisations, such as the United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East (UNRWA) and the OCHA, have played a vital role in assisting. They have supplied food, healthcare and accommodations. Nevertheless, they have also encountered significant casualties, with numerous personnel, such as teachers, physicians and healthcare professionals, dying in the process. At least 543 relief workers have died since October 2023, including 373 UN officials and team members (UN 2025a). ActionAid, Oxfam, War Child, Save the Children, CARE, Norwegian Refugee Council, Médecins du Monde, and Humanity and Inclusion/Handicap International are some of the NGOs working in aid operations in Gaza.

Diplomatic Efforts

The way countries have responded diplomatically to the crises in Ukraine and Gaza has been starkly different. This is because of their geopolitical alignments, historical ties, and strategic objectives. This has led to claims that Western countries have 'double standards' when it comes to following international law. Mainly because of US support to Israel in Gaza actions and opposing Russia at the same time.

Ukraine: Peace talks, sanctions, and mediation efforts

Western countries strongly and unanimously condemned Russia's invasion of Ukraine and imposed heavy sanctions in response. During the initial phase of the Ukraine conflict, notable diplomatic efforts were

undertaken, such as convening meetings in Belarus and Turkey. Negotiations nearly resulted in a resolution; however, they collapsed in May 2022 (Charap and Radchenko 2024). The UN and other countries across the world were calling for an immediate ceasefire. The Black Sea Grain Initiative, which the UN and Turkey arranged in July 2022, was a significant diplomatic success (Mugoni et al. 2025, 5). It made it possible for Ukrainian grain to be safely exported from ports that were blocked, which helped with worldwide food shortages. However, Russia attacked the port of Odesa just hours after signing the accord and then talks stopped.

The US, UK, and EU quickly put in place strict sanctions against Russia that affected people, banks, enterprises, and important economic sectors, including energy and banking. The goal of these steps was to isolate Russia economically from the rest of the world and to make it pay for its aggression. Russia responded with counter-sanctions, including a ban on food exports, which harmed Europe's economy (Roy 2023). Different diplomatic responses differ sharply. For example, Russia has coordinated Western sanctions and diplomatic isolation, whereas Gaza has more fragmented international action. This leads to different legal paths, leverage, and humanitarian effects.

Gaza: UN resolutions, ceasefire negotiations, and regional diplomacy

The diplomatic response to the crisis in Gaza has been very divided. Most Western countries support Israel's 'right to defend itself,' but many other countries say its measures are too harsh and amount to genocide. Unlike in Ukraine, there hasn't been much agreement among Western nations on calling for a ceasefire in Gaza. The US has used its veto power in the UN Security Council many times to stop resolutions that called for an urgent humanitarian ceasefire. The UK has not voted in favour of similar measures. The EU has requested humanitarian pauses, but not a complete ceasefire (Maulana 2024, 38). This unwillingness to act quickly is very different from the quick calls for a ceasefire in Ukraine, which have received criticism. The US, until March 2025, vetoed and blocked the UNSC resolutions calling for an immediate ceasefire. The International Court of Justice (ICJ), on a complaint from South Africa accusing Israel of genocide, told Israel to stop genocide and let humanitarian aid enter Gaza. At the same time, the International Criminal Court (ICC) in November 2024 issued arrest warrants for Israeli PM Benjamin Netanyahu and former Defence Minister Gallant for war crimes, such as using hunger as a weapon of war. These moves have put more diplomatic pressure on Israel and its allies.

BUILDING A COHERENT RESPONSE: A LEGAL AND POLICY ROADMAP

A collection of international laws and human rights documents constitutes the rules for keeping civilians, refugees, and the displaced safely in war zones. However, the use and implementation of these guidelines have not been consistent, which has led to claims of ‘double standards’ in how the crises in Ukraine and Gaza have been handled.

International Refugee Law

The 1951 Refugee Convention (and 1967 Protocol), the Geneva Conventions and customary International Humanitarian Law (IHL) are all important legal frameworks that protect people from things like non-refoulement and civilian harm. The 1967 Protocol removed the Convention’s geographical and chronological constraints, which had only applied to European refugees from events prior to 1951. In Ukraine’s case, the EU and its member states have largely adhered to the spirit of the Convention. The EU turned on its Temporary Protection Directive because so many Ukrainians were coming in at once. This gave them immediate status and rights, skipping the long individual asylum processes (Schrooten 2025, 1-2). The situation is legally complicated for Palestinians. UNRWA, not UNHCR, is responsible for most of the refugees in Gaza. This independent UN agency was set up before the 1951 Convention to help Palestinians who were forced to leave their homes in 1948. This has led to a ‘*protection gap*’ because UNRWA’s job doesn’t involve protecting people legally or finding long-term solutions, which are two of UNHCR’s main jobs (Irfan 2023, 4–5, 38). Implementation gaps (such as the difference between UNRWA’s humanitarian mandate and UNHCR’s protection mandate) make Palestinian refugees more vulnerable and need specific policy responses.

The Geneva Conventions and Protections for Civilians

The Geneva Conventions of 1949 and IHL set regulations to keep civilians safe during wars. These rules say that attacks on non-combatants and civilian infrastructure, including homes, schools, and hospitals, are not allowed; they have been violated in both Ukraine and Gaza. IHL clearly says that starving civilians is not a way to fight. Human Rights Watch and other groups have said that Israel’s entire siege of Gaza breaks this rule and is a war crime because it punishes everyone at once (Abudayya 2025, 2). Even though it is a crime, there are claims that Russia has forcibly moved hundreds of thousands of Ukrainians, including children, to Russian territories that Russia controls. The displacement of more than 90 per cent of the people in Gaza, which was caused by Israeli instructions to evacuate to ‘humanitarian zones’ that were later attacked, has also raised severe concerns under IHL.

CONCLUSION

This analysis has looked at the many problems in Ukraine and Gaza, including the effects on civilians, the response from other countries, and the laws that regulate these situations. The findings reveal widespread catastrophes, resulting in significant human suffering and challenges to international protection systems. Displacement has far-reaching socio-economic impacts on both host communities and refugees, affecting employment, education and social cohesion. There have been refugee protection laws, but in the present context, they need to be evaluated, and this evaluation needs to be conducted at the regional level, involving all parties. The old refugee rules are still not a sound legal foundation since they only offer partial protection for what should be a rare situation.

In Gaza, civilian casualties are staggering, with the healthcare system in absolute disarray, and a restricted food supply has created a famine situation. The war in Ukraine has also destroyed key infrastructure, leaving millions of people in need of help and security. Despite an extreme situation, those affected have shown incredible strength through culturally ingrained coping mechanisms, including community cooperation, religious faith (*sabr*), storytelling, and improvised psychosocial support in Gaza. Abudayya (2025) notes that these actions are not solely for survival; they constitute means of '*moral and political resistance*' against dehumanisation. In Ukraine, the rapid mobilisation of civil society, volunteer networks, and a substantial diaspora provided refugees with important early assistance, often more quickly than formal institutions.

It is crucial to adhere to international law and ensure that humanitarian access remains unobstructed. Additionally, we must work to eliminate political interference in aid efforts, empowering local and diaspora entities by enhancing coordination. International collaboration and equitable burden-sharing should facilitate sustainable solutions that encompass protection, integration, and reconstruction activities, thereby alleviating stress on host regions. It is necessary to prioritise the mental health of the affected and to conduct further research on long-term impacts, integration models, digital repatriation, and the most effective means of delivering aid. Most importantly, diplomacy and dialogue are a must.

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AUTHOR

Aman Bora
Ph.D. Candidate (JRF),
Department of Political Science
SSJDWSSS Government P.G. College Ranikhet, Almora, Uttarakhand.

Inclusive